

NEW METHODS AND ANALYSES OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Gazieva Shakhnoza

Teacher of the department of Language of Samarkand Zarmed University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14284942>

Abstract. This article discusses new methods and techniques of the communicative approach in learning foreign languages. It provides information based on analyses of the essence of the communicative approach, the effectiveness of modern methods and techniques in the learning process, and the mobility of an innovative methodological approach in language learning.

Key words: communicative approach, interactive method, stimulation, mobility, context, gamification.

НОВЫЕ МЕТОДЫ И АНАЛИЗ КОММУНИКАТИВНОГО ПОДХОДА В ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются новые методы и приемы коммуникативного подхода в изучении иностранных языков. В ней представлена информация, основанная на анализе сущности коммуникативного подхода, эффективности современных методов и приемов в процессе обучения, а также мобильности инновационного методического подхода в изучении языка.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативный подход, интерактивный метод, стимуляция, мобильность, контекст, геймификация.

CHET TILLARINI O'RGANISHDA KOMMUNIKATIV YONDASHUVNING YANGI USULLARI VA TAHLILLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda kommunikativ yondashuvning yangicha usul va metodlari to'g'risida fikr yuritilgan. Unda kommunikativ yondashuvning mohiyati, zamonaviy usullar va metodlarning o'quv jarayonidagi samaradorligi, innovatsion metodik yondashuvning til o'rganishdagi mobilligi borasida tahlillar asosida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kommunikativ yondashuv, interaktiv metod, stimulyatsiya, mobillik, kontekst, gamifikatsiya.

INTRODUCTION

Learning a foreign language is a process that requires not only memorizing grammatical rules, but also mastering all speech activities in the language. The communicative approach (CTA) is one of the effective methods of learning a foreign language, which is aimed at teaching the student to effectively use the language in real-life situations. Today, the methodology of language learning is a constantly evolving process, and new methods of the communicative approach allow making the language teaching process more effective.

MAIN PART

1. The essence of the communicative approach. The communicative approach is characterized as a methodology focused primarily on communication in language learning. The main goal of this method is to teach the student not only to know the grammatical rules of the language, but also to effectively use that language in a social context. The communicative

approach bases language learning directly on speech activity, that is, listening, speaking, reading and writing. The main idea of the communicative approach is to focus not on learning the language as such, but on using the language in real life situations. Thus, the learning process does not consist of accumulating grammar and vocabulary, but in communicating using existing skills and abilities.

The communicative approach is based on the idea that successful language learning occurs through the need to convey real meaning. When learners are engaged in real communication, their natural language acquisition strategies will be activated, and this will enable them to learn to use the language.

2. New methods and techniques. With the development of modern technologies and multimedia tools in interactive methods, the opportunity to organize interactive classes for students has increased. These methods ensure the active involvement of students in the language learning process, for example, using video materials, games, online conversations and simulations, which significantly increase the effectiveness of language learning.

Task-based learning: This method allows students to use language in real-life situations. For example, students actively learn the language while working on a project or solving a specific situation.

Communicative conversation method: The main goal of language teaching in this method is to be in constant communication. Students are given the opportunity to talk freely, which helps them feel confident in the process of learning the language.

Learning lexical and grammatical interdependence: Students are taught to connect lexical and grammatical systems, to understand the logical and structural aspects of the language. With this method, they not only learn grammar, but also develop the ability to understand and respond in real conversations.

Cognitive approach: This approach focuses on developing students' mental activity and analytical approach to mastering new knowledge in the process of learning a language. At the same time, it helps students develop their memory and conscious learning abilities.

3. Innovations in the methodological approach. Today, one of the effective ways to use new methods of the communicative approach in the process of learning foreign languages is the mobility of language learning. With the help of mobile applications, online courses and virtual classrooms, students have the opportunity to learn a language at any time and anywhere. Also, gamification of exercises helps to make the language learning process interesting and motivating.

English is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. It is used in both business and personal life. Learning English can be very useful for career advancement, traveling, communicating with native speakers, and many other purposes. There are many methods for learning English, but not all of them are equally effective. In this article, we will look at some of the most effective methods for learning English.

Learning a language through reading is one of the most effective methods for learning English. Reading helps improve your understanding of grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure. In addition, reading helps improve pronunciation and intonation. To use this method, you need to choose a book or article in English that matches your level of language proficiency. Reading should be regular, every day if possible. Learning a language through listening - listening to audio and video materials in English is another effective method for learning a language. This method helps improve your understanding of English speech, pronunciation, and intonation.

To use this method, you need to choose audio or video materials in English that match your level of language proficiency. Listening should be done regularly, every day if possible. Learning

a language through communication with native speakers - communication with native speakers is one of the most effective methods of learning English. This method helps to improve your understanding of English speech, pronunciation and intonation, as well as improve your communication skills in English.

To use this method, you need to find a native English speaker and start communicating with him in English. Communication should be regular, every day if possible. An effective method for learning English depends on your personal preferences and goals. However, reading, listening and communicating with native speakers are the most effective methods of learning English that will help improve your proficiency in the language.

CONCLUSION

The communicative approach is an effective approach that includes new methods and techniques in learning a foreign language. Today, technological developments, interactive and experiential learning methods increase the effectiveness of language learning. Students not only learn the language, but also learn to effectively use it in real life. In order for this approach to be more successful in the future, methods and techniques must be constantly updated.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Tsaryk, O., Panychok, T., Rybina, N., Koshil, N. (2023). Interactive methods of learning a foreign language: the role of the communicative approach.
2. Sidorova, Irina Gennadyevna. "Communicative and pragmatic characteristics of genres of personal Internet discourse (website, blog, social network, comment)." URL: [https://av. disus. ru/dissertatsiya/1196021-1-kommunikativno-pragmaticheskie-harakteristiki-zhanrov-personalgotinternet-diskursa-sayt-blog-socialnaya-set-komentariy. php](https://av.disus.ru/dissertatsiya/1196021-1-kommunikativno-pragmaticheskie-harakteristiki-zhanrov-personalgotinternet-diskursa-sayt-blog-socialnaya-set-komentariy.php) (2014).
3. Шахноза, Г. А. (2023). OPINIONS AND CONSIDERATIONS ON THE STUDY OF ERGATIVE VERBS. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 6(2).
4. Rosenthal, Alan S., and Robert A. Sloane. "A communicative approach to foreign language instruction: The UMBC project." *Foreign Language Annals* (1987): 245-253.
5. Шахноза, Г. А. (2023). OPINIONS AND CONSIDERATIONS ON THE STUDY OF ERGATIVE VERBS. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 6(2).
6. Lebedeva, Maria Yuryevna. "Digital revolution in linguodidactics of Russian as a foreign language: some linguistic and methodological aspects." *Current issues of description and teaching of Russian as a foreign/non-native language* (2018): 580.
7. Shakhnoza, G. (2024). FORMS OF ACTION IN THE ENGLISH VERB SYSTEM. *ILM-FAN YANGILIKLARI KONFERENSIYASI*, 2(1), 114-116.
8. Колобкова, Анастасия Анатольевна. "Исторический экскурс становления и развития методики преподавания иностранных языков в российских университетах." *Педагогический журнал* 9.4-1 (2019): 73.
9. Almazova, N. I. (2003). Cognitive aspects of the formation of intercultural competence in teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university.
10. Abduvasievna, G. S., Habibdjanovna, B. D., Karimovna, Y. S. (2021). Foreign Language Teachers in the System of Public Education. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 7001-7010.